

Analyzing the Factors by One-Way ANOVA Associated with Plain Weft Knitted Fabrics' Production

Meheraz Zannat

Department of Sciences, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology, Bangladesh

Md. Alimur Reza ✉

Department of Textile Engineering & Management, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology, Bangladesh

Tareq Iqbal

Department of Textile Engineering, Sheikh Rehana Textile Engineering College, Bangladesh

Sabrina Shahrin Swarna

Department of Textile Engineering Management, Bangladesh University of Textiles, Bangladesh

Dilshat Rubia Dola

Department of Textile Engineering, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology, Bangladesh

Easir Al Afroz

Department of Textile Engineering & Management, BGMEA University of Fashion and Technology, Bangladesh

Rabeya Wazed Pushpita

Department of Textile Engineering, Daffodil International University, Bangladesh

Suggested Citation

Zannat, M., Reza, M.A., Iqbal, T., Swarna, S.S., Dola, D.R., Al Afroz, E., & Pushpita, R.W. (2024). Analyzing the Factors by One-Way ANOVA Associated with Plain Weft Knitted Fabrics' Production. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(5), 167-173. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(5\).17](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(5).17)

Abstract:

Bangladesh has achieved a significant reputation for RMG exporting over the last three decades, particularly in knitwear. The knitwear sector is one of the self-supporting sectors of Bangladesh, which could meet 90% of the fabric requirements. However, there is an empirical relationship between machine diameter and fabric diameter. It's assumed that the machine diameter determines the fabric diameter. Therefore, the objectives of the study were to test the significance of average shifting in fabric diameter from machine diameter and the overall effect of machine diameter on fabric diameter. Empirical research has been conducted for such an investigation. This study was carried out with a few factories and a

full lot of each factory was inspected. Based on the collected data, diameters of machines were grouped into three levels to understand the variation of fabric diameters. Then, SPSS software was used to analyze the collected data, applying one sample t test and one-way ANOVA. However, the result of the analysis revealed that machine diameter has no effect but indicative means reduction were found in fabric diameters. In the future, more comprehensive studies could be done by including larger data. But now, these findings will help all the personnel related to the quality and production of knitted fabric.

Keywords: *Knit fabric, machine diameter, fabric diameter, one sample t test, one-way ANOVA.*

Introduction

Williams Lee was the first to construct a knitting frame in the 15th century. The invention of cams, needles, gauges, sinkers, take-downs, feeders, and other items continued throughout the century. Bangladesh's textile industry has grown at a rate of 21% per year on average since 1978. During this time, the knitting industry experienced even more expansion. However, knitted materials have poorer dimensional qualities than woven fabrics. Dimensional qualities are mostly determined by machine settings, yarn count, and stitch length. (Khan, 2015), (Lyer, 1995), (Munden, 1959). Though different mathematical and geometrical equations are used theoretically, the process parameters in industrial production yielded mixed results, despite the employment of several mathematical and geometrical equations in theory. To get the desired GSM, the producer must adjust the stitch length and yarn count in accordance with machine parameters, particularly the diameter and gauge. (Abedin, 2014). Due to the different process sequences after the take-down of the grey fabric from the machine, the characteristics of the plain weft knitted fabric change. But all the parameters cannot be controlled during the manufacturing process. This study will try to find out the key predictors for GSM and the diameter of the fabrics. Geometric constant is suggested from geometry of plain weft knitted fabrics (Anbumani N. , 2007). This study found significant relation of among the different parameters of plain weft knitted fabrics with the setting of knitting machines. This finding will help the manufacturer to use the most significant parameters that will help to set the desired properties of fabric. Correlation and regression method is used here by manufacturing plain weft knitted fabrics in a different setting, machine specification, resultant count and stitch length. First correlation coefficients are analyzed and significant factors are determined at 1% and 5% level of significance. And regression models are developed for grey diameter, finished width, finished GSM and geometrical constant. Due to unobserved parameters, and to find the combined effect of resultant count and stitch

length, new variables geometric constant was also considered in this study. Here, geometric constant represents the final equation that will be helpful to determine GSM with the help of predetermined stitch length and resultant count in tex.

Literature Review

Because of its superior air permeability conductivity and insulation qualities, weft knitted fabric has become more popular than woven materials. With diverse patterning and design, it captures the attention of the modern style with low manufacturing costs and no need for ironing; high stretch and elasticity that conforms to body movement; excellent resistance to bursting, crease, and wear; and excellent resistance to bursting, crease, and wear. As a result, it is gradually replacing woven materials. (Anbumani N. , 2007). But, the properties of weft knitted fabrics depend on the parameters set in the machines. Due to its poor dimensional stability, many experiments have taken to establish the required parameters in the machine to limit the variation and get the desired characteristics in the finished fabrics (Zakaria, 2012). Some of them discussed effect of yarn count and machine parameter, tightness factor, relaxation, finishing process and rate of feeding on spirality. These also influence fabric width, stitch length and GSM for various counts (Kothari, 2011). Structural changes in knits during processing, the dimensional stability of plain knitted fabrics and the different properties related to machine parameters are studied to find out their relationships. Careful machine adjustment can alleviate difficulties caused by excessive shrinkage (Black, 1974). Machine gauge influences the number of wales in the fabrics also affect physical and mechanical properties of knitted fabrics (Haque, 2014). Different fabric structures can be created depending on the yarn shape and yarn path. Knit fabric dimensional stability is a crucial aspect of the knitting business. The dimensional stability of cloth is influenced by stitch length, yarn count, and fabric structure. As a result of the machine parameters selected, fabric qualities such as GSM, grey diameter, finishing width, spirality, and shrinkage vary. (Parmer,

1999). Many researches were performed to investigate the effect of different knitting parameters on the physical and mechanical properties of knitted fabrics (Peirce, 1937). This study is designed to determine the significant predictor for the fabric diameter/width, GSM, the geometric constant of plain weft knitted fabrics.

Objective

In this research, one sample t test and one-way analysis of variance (Montgomery, 2003) were conducted to analyze the effect of machine diameter on fabric diameter and the objectives are-

- To compare the mean fabric diameter to a fixed machine diameter.
- To test the main effect of machine diameter on fabric diameter.

Materials and Method

Terms Related to Machine Parameters

1. **Machine gauge:** Machine gauge can be calculated by dividing the total number of needles into the length of the needle bed. The number of needles or tricks in the needle bed per inch (Ajgaonkar, 2006)
2. **Machine diameter:** It varies on the type and width of the fabric requires. The distance from one needle head or butt to the just opposite needle head or butt is termed as machine diameter. Machine gauge and diameter determine the total number of needles and the fabric width (Anbumani, 2007).
3. **Needles:** In circular weft knitting machine latch needles are widely used.
4. **Feeder:** Yarn guides placed close to the needles to the full circumference of the knitting zone (Anbumani, 2007).

Related to Fabrics Specifications

1. **Plain weft knitted fabrics:** The weft knitted fabrics produced with one set of needles (both in tubular or flat forms) are called as single jersey or plain knitted fabrics (Ajgaonkar, 2006).

5. Fabric width/diameter: Fabric is taken down from the circular knitting machine in tubular form then the diameter of the fabric tube is called fabric dia. And when tube is slitted off to open width the fabric width in open form is found (Anbumani, 2007).

One Sample t-Test

In a one sample test of means, a sample's mean is compared to a predetermined or hypothesized value, and any deviation from the value is examined. When population standard deviation is unknown and sample size is small ($n < 30$) then t statistic is applicable. Then this statistical test is referred as one sample t test or single sample t test. The testing of hypothesis is:

$$H_0: \mu = \mu_0$$

$$H_1: \mu \neq \mu_0$$

Where, μ_0 is the hypothesized or proposed value of the population mean. So, one sample t test means testing whether a sample mean differs significantly from a known population mean or not and the conditions are: test variable that is continuous (i.e., interval or ratio level), independence of observations, random sample of data from the population, normal distribution (approximately), homogeneity of variances, no outliers.

One-Way ANOVA

Analysis of variance, abbreviated to ANOVA is a powerful statistical method which was developed in 1920 by the statistician Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher, who is the "Father of Modern Statistics and Experimental Design" This method is used to compare variances across the means of different groups or levels or the means of three or more populations based on the variation found in the experimental data or observations, and the overall variation found in the observations is split up into two components representing two different categories of variations: one is the variation resulting from assignable causes and another is chance causes.

Apart from chance causes, when there is just one assignable cause or factor that accounts for the variation in the observations of the data, then this is called the one-way analysis of variance or

one-way ANOVA. This test is also known as: one-factor ANOVA, between subjects ANOVA. This single factor is separated into several levels or groups, each of which is utilized for a different subset of sampling units. One-way ANOVA ascertains the impact of these groups on the outcome, by examining whether the response varies across the factor's levels or not, As a consequence, suppose A denotes only one factor with k different levels and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_k$ are the population mean effects of these k levels. Now, the testing of hypothesis according to the one-way ANOVA is:

$$H_0: \alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_k \quad (\text{all } k \text{ means are equal})$$

$$H_1: \text{At least one } \alpha_i \text{ is different}$$

(at least one of the k population means is not equal to others)

Where,

α_i is the population mean of the i^{th} level ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$). The F test statistic is used regarding the testing.

One-Way ANOVA Model with Assumptions and Post-Hoc Test

A model is necessary for every statistical test of form in order to test the null hypothesis that there is no form. ANOVA serves as an exploratory method in the search for the best-fitting model with significant explanatory variables Here, the statistical model for one-way ANOVA is:

$$y_{ij} = \mu + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{ij}$$

Where,

y_{ij} represents outcome of j^{th} observation due to i^{th} level.

μ is the general mean effect or overall average effect.

α_i is the mean effect of the level A_i of the factor A .

$\varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$ represents random error (random effect in the j^{th} observation on the i^{th} level)

Now the assumptions to conduct one-way ANOVA are:

dependent variable is continuous (interval or ratio level of measurement) and independent variable or single factor is categorical, random sample of data from the population, independence of observations (observation in one group cannot be in another group. No group can influence the other group), no outliers are present in the data, normal distribution (approximately) of the dependent variable for each group (i.e., for each level of the factor), homogeneity of variances (i.e., variances approximately equal across groups/levels).

In Latin, post-hoc means 'after this'. The preliminary analysis simply suggests whether or not the means test has overall significance. Rather, a post-hoc test can be used to determine which particular groups or levels differ from one another across the means if a significant result is found. That's why multiple comparison tests is another term for post-hoc test. Bonferroni's test, Scheffe's test, Tukey's honest significant difference test (Tukey's HSD test), etc. are some examples of post-hoc tests.

Research Design

In real life, approval to collect data from any industry is tough, though a few industries allowed and one full lot was inspected from each industry. According to the objectives of the research, one sample t test and one-way analysis of variance were applied and total 21 observations were collected where, three different machine diameters with a fixed gauge (36x18, 38x18 and 40x18) was found. In this exploration, IBM SPSS statistics (version 26) was engaged.

During collection of the data the standard temperature $27 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity $65 \pm 2\%$ is considered as tropical country.

Apparatus or Materials

100% cotton 25 single jersey fabrics form single ply and double ply yarn of resultant count ranges from 14.76 tex to 32.81 tex using single jersey machines whose specifications are 26D×20G, 26D×24G, 30D×20G, 30D×24G, 34D×20G, 34D×24G, 36D×20G, 38D×20G and 38D×24G with a different stitch length ranges from 2.4 mm to 3.05 mm with available facilities. **Standards used:** BS 1932:1953 for fabric width

(Anon, 1963b), B.S. 2471:1954 for weight per unit length (Anon, 1963a).

Result and Discussion

Primarily, inspection was started with descriptive statistics and one sample t test (Table 1). Irrespective of all the machine diameters average fabric diameter was found 35.29 with standard deviation 2.80.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics and One Sample t test of Fabric Diameter

Machine diameter	Frequency of fabric produced (<i>n</i>)	Result of fabric diameter under each machine diameter				<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	99% CI of the mean difference		Effect size
		<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>MIN</i>	<i>MAX</i>				LL	UL	
36	7	35.86	1.68	34	38	0.23	6	.829	33.51	38.21	.085
38	7	34.86	3.24	32	40	2.57	6	.042	30.32	39.39	.97
40	7	35.14	3.49	30	39	3.69	6	.010	30.26	40.03	1.39

Note: $\sum n = 21$. *M* = mean, *SD* = standard deviation, *MIN* = minimum, *MAX* = maximum, LL = Lower limit, UL = Upper limit.; effect size → Cohen's *D*.; **p* < .01.

Empirically, the machine diameter determines the fabric diameter. But there is a small allowance of deviation (stretch or shrink) in fabric diameter from machine diameter. These non-significant one sample t test results (Table 1) proved this statement, under 1% allowance. But only shrinkages were noticed when diameters of machine were getting increased. Moreover, at 5% allowance, significant results

were found for 38 and 40 machine diameters (*t* = 2.57, *p* = .042 and *t* = 3.68, *p* = .010). Further, this research investigated the effect of machine diameter (Table 2) and considering the above situation, this result showed a non-significant effect. An equivalent means of fabric diameter (Table 1) was the reason of this ineffectiveness (Table 2).

Table 2. Results of One-Way ANOVA for Fabric Diameter with the Necessary Assumptions Testing

Source	SS	MS	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P</i>	η_p^2	Observed power
Machine diameter	3.72	1.86	2	0.22	.805	.024	.079
Within groups or Error	152.57	8.48	18				
Total	156.29		20				

*R*² = 0.03, Adjusted *R*² = 0.09, Test of homogeneity of variances (Levene statistic: based on median = 1.84, *p* = .188) Shapiro–Wilk test of normality under each machine diameter (*p* values: .215, .163, .379 for 36, 38 and 40 machine diameters respectively)

Note: SS = Sum of Squares (Type III), MS = Mean Sum of Squares, *df* = Degrees of freedom, η_p^2 = Partial eta squared (effect size) (Brown, 2008); Requirements of test of homogeneity of variances (Parra-Frutos, 2013) and Shapiro-Wilk test of normality (Razali N.M., 2015) were fulfilled. **p* < .01.

Even effect size implied 2.4% ($0.01 \leq \eta_p^2 \leq 0.06$, indicated small effect) of variance was

accounted for by the machine diameter with observed power .079. Though post-hoc test was

not a requirement anymore, figure 1 visualized the average fabric diameters which steeped straightly down from 36 to 38 and not raised that much for 40 machine diameter.

Figure 1. Mean Plot of Fabric Diameter According to each Machine Diameter

Limitation

This experiment was done completely relying on the factory's permission to collect data, and researchers were bound not to play any role when production was in progress. That's why choosing the diameters of the machine was not in the researcher's hands. So, the size of the collected data was small and a few differences were found in machine diameters only for a fixed machine gauge.

Further research

Since result was non-significant, a further attempt can be taken based on large data with more different machine diameters and gauges to find out significant difference if exists.

Conclusion

Practically, the fabric diameter is primarily fixed by the effects of machine diameter and gauge. But based on the real data, this effectiveness was missing. A dramatical mean reduction in the fabric diameters was observed while the machine diameters were increased, and discrepancy from

the machine diameter was also prominent. Even with the increasing level of significance fabric diameter was getting out of the allowance of deviation. But it should be around machine diameter. So along with the fixed gauge, the diameter of the machine may cause a lot of shrinkage in fabric diameter, which was not expected.

References

- Abedin, F. M. (2014). Effect of gauge variation of circular knitting machine on physical and mechanical properties of cotton knitted fabrics. *International Journal of Textile Science*, 3(1), 10-13. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.textile.20140301.03>
- Ajgaonkar, D. B. (2006). *Quality and calculations for weft-knits*. In *Knitting technology* (3rd ed.). Bombay: Universal Publishing Corporation.
- Anbumani, N. (2007). *Knitting fundamentals, machines, structures, and developments*. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Limited.
- Anbumani, N. (2007). Calculations in weft knitting. In *Knitting fundamentals, machines, structures, and developments*. New Delhi: New Age International (P) Limited.
- Anon. (1963). Determination of width of woven or knitted fabrics. *Methods of Test for Textiles*.
- Black, M. B. (1974). Shrinkage control for cotton and cotton blend knitted fabrics. *Textile Research Journal*, 44(10), 729-737. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004051757404401004>
- Brown, J. D. (2008). Statistics corner. Questions and answers about language testing statistics: Effect size and eta squared. *Shiken: JALT Testing & Evaluation SIG Newsletter*, 12(2), 38-43.
- Cochran, W. G. (2000). *Experimental design* (2nd ed.). New Delhi: John Wiley & Sons.
- Cohen, J. (1968). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (Vol. 16). Hillsdale, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.

- Ganesh, H., Velayudhan, C., & Sudhakar, C. (2018). P-values, P-values everywhere. *Current Science*, 115(3), 452-454.
- Hand, D. J. (1987). *Multivariate analysis of variance and repeated measures: A practical approach for behavioural scientists*. New York: Chapman and Hall.
- Haque, I., & Amin, M. (2014). Selection of suitable machine gauge by considering the GSM, shrinkage, and spirality of single jersey knit fabric. *Research Journal of Science & IT Management*, 3(1), 12-20.
- Hilton, A., & Armstrong, R. A. (2006). Statnote 6: post-hoc ANOVA tests. *Microbiologist*, 7(1), 34-36.
- Hochberg, Y., & Tamhane, A. C. (1987). *Multiple comparison procedures*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Keppel, G., & Wickens, T. D. (2004). *Design and analysis: A researcher's handbook* (4th ed.). Pearson.
- Khan, Z. R. (2015). Human before the garment: Bangladesh tragedy revisited, ethical manufacturing or lack thereof in garment manufacturing industry. *World Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(1), 29-43.
- Knaub, J. R. (1987). Practical interpretation of hypothesis tests. *The American Statistician*, 41(3), 217-220. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2684316>
- Kothari, V. S. (2011). Spirality of cotton plain knitted fabric with respect to variation in yarn and machine parameters. *Indian Journal of Fibre and Textile Research*, 36(3), 322-327.
- Lyer, M. H., & A. B. King. (1995). *Fundamentals of stitch formation*. In *Circular knitting* (pp. 25-37). Bamberg, Germany: Meisenbach GmbH.
- Mangiafico, S. (2016). *Summary and analysis of extension program evaluation in R* (version 1.19.10). Rutgers Cooperative Extension, New Brunswick, NJ.
- Montgomery, D. C. (2003). *Design and analysis of experiments* (6th ed.). Wiley.
- Munden, D. L. (1959). The geometry and dimensional properties of plain knit fabrics. *Journal of the Textile Institute*, 50(5), 448-471. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19447025908659287>
- Norton, B. J. (1986). Guide for the interpretation of two-way analysis of variance. *Journal of Educational Statistics*, 11(4), 363-372. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1164728>
- Parmer, A. M. (1999). An unconventional way to incorporate comfort in knitted fabrics. *Indian Journal of Fibre & Textile Research*, 24(2), 79-84.
- Parra-Frutos, I. (2013). Testing homogeneity of variances with unequal sample sizes. *Computational Statistics & Data Analysis*, 57(3), 249-258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2012.06.006>
- Peirce, F. T. (1937). The geometry of cloth structure. *Journal of the Textile Institute Transactions*, 28(3), T45-T96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19447023708658788>
- Pituch, K. A., & Stevens, J. P. (2016). *Applied multivariate statistics for the social sciences: Analysis with SAS and IBM's SPSS* (6th ed.). Routledge.
- Razali, N. M., & Wah, Y. B. (2011). Power comparisons of Shapiro-Wilk, Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Lilliefors and Anderson-Darling tests. *Journal of Statistical Modeling and Analytics*, 2(1), 21-33.
- Spencer, D. F. (2001). *An introduction to textile technology*. New York: Wiley.
- Zakaria, K., & Mohd, K. (2012). Effect of machine parameters on knit fabric specifications. *DUET Journal*, 2(1), 36-42.